

MODERN BUILDING MATERIALS IMAGE OF THE COUNTRY AND THE PEOPLE QUALITY OF LIFE IS GUARANTEED.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7956402>

Annotation. It is no secret to anyone that the development of tourism and the image of the country in the new era of Uzbekistan's economy is a priority task of our republic. Modern construction, buildings and structures cannot be imagined without new types of building materials. In today's global environment, the improvement of living standards and the pursuit of high quality standards do not exclude the construction industry, as it does in all industries.

Urban planning and architecture are the main factor in increasing tourism potential.

Key words: economy, small business, development, Republic of Uzbekistan.

Our country, whose history goes back several thousand years, has long been worthy of the high recognition of the people of the world with its urban planning and architectural monuments, because the words "Saikali roi zamin" did not just appear. However, all aspects of humanity continue to develop rapidly. Including: architecture, urban planning architecture.

Today, countries in our region such as China, Singapore, Japan, Qatar, and the United Arab Emirates are leading in these fields. The countries mentioned above are attracting the people of the world due to their achievements in the field. According to the results of social surveys, the majority of visitors to the United Arab Emirates stated that the main reason for their visit was the desire to see the Burj Khalifa. People who traveled to Singapore recorded their impressions of the world's most environmentally friendly metropolis.

In recent years, the attention paid to the tourism sector by the leadership of our country and the efforts made to turn this sector into an important direction of the country's economy, urban planning and architecture occupy an important place.

After all, today it is difficult to impress and attract humanity only with ancient achievements and heritage of ancestors. Not being able to live up to the ancestors who achieved great achievements is also painful.

Construction materials account for up to 60% of the cost of construction work.

Modern architecture requires new, high-quality and cheap, light and earthquake-resistant, beautiful and innovative products. The scale of the creative works carried out in our country in recent years is a proof of the high importance of the building materials production sector.

In this direction, important initiatives and reforms are being implemented in order to reach new sources. The President of our Republic has adopted decrees and decisions on the improvement of construction and assembly works for 2018-2021. Among them, the most important is the decision PQ-4198 of February 20, 2019 on "Measures for radical improvement and comprehensive development of the construction materials industry", according to which the association "Uzsanoatqurilishmateriallari" was established.

"Uzsanoatqurilishmateriallari" association provides full use of all types of building materials: cement, lime, gypsum, wall-to-wall roofing, waterproofing and heat-retaining materials from more than 100 types of basic construction products. The association provides technical, economic and informational support to its enterprises aimed at introducing and developing new types of products, working closely with foreign companies, attracting high technologies.

With the support of the association, during the past period, fundamental reforms were implemented in the field of building materials industry, and as a result of them, local manufacturers created new types of innovative export and import-substituting construction materials - paper, liquid paper, zoloblock, gasoblock . , foam block, polyester block, asbestos-free composite slate, refractory brick, soft roofing materials, insulating materials, basalt fittings, fiber, mesh, fritta, decorative paints, stone, glass, ceramic types of mosaics, sports and household linoleum, fiberglass, fiberglass mesh, waterproofing materials, geo-textile, geomembrane, gentonite mat and geocompost production.

In order to introduce innovations to the construction materials industry, the study and use of international best practices was launched. As a result, translucent concrete, new type of construction glass, chameleon brick, glass tile, quartz vinyl flooring, plastic mold for concrete pouring, composite liquid thermal insulation coatings are widely used in construction, capital repair and design works. . In order to introduce the achievements of science into the production process of new types of innovative building materials, advanced specialists of research and higher education institutions are being attracted to the field. At the same time, international standards were adopted in order to introduce the production of high-quality and safe building materials. More than 1000 international standards were adopted in 2020-2021 alone. As a result, alignment with international standards in the network has increased significantly.

The increase in demographics naturally causes an increase in the demand and need for construction materials.

According to population statistics, in 2022, the population of our republic will exceed 36 million and will continue to grow by 900,000 annually. These numbers require a huge supply base from all sectors of the economy, including construction and construction.

In meeting the needs of the population, it is important to focus not on numbers, but on quality, factors such as safety and comfort.

The natural disasters occurring on our planet and the anomalous vagaries of the climate require deep research and a serious approach from experts in the field.

It has been proven to be an effective method to take a model from the direction of developed countries in the economy . However, natural disasters that have occurred in the world in recent days show that even the countries that are considered to be advanced leaders in construction and urban development are not free from mistakes and shortcomings. Therefore, drawing conclusions from mistakes and shortcomings in creating a national model using the achievements of developed countries is also an urgent issue.

In short, since ancient times, mankind has been striving for beauty and comfort, so the desire of our people to build beautiful and comfortable houses is a characteristic of mankind. Handy, naturally creative people have the right to live in Smarthouses and work in Hi-Tech buildings, using all the achievements of science and technology in the global world. After all, a quality apartment, a quality environment is a part of the quality level of life that we strive for.

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